

Kinetics and mechanism of the interaction of thioglycolic acid with *cis*-diaquaethylenediamineplatinum(II) perchlorate in aqueous medium

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Manuscript received 6 January 1998, revised 17 June 1998, accepted 2 July 1998

The kinetics of the interaction of thioglycolic acid with $[\text{Pt en}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$ has been studied spectrophotometrically as a function of $[\text{Pt en}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$, [thioglycolic acid], pH and temperature. The reaction has been monitored at 224 nm, where the spectral difference between the reactants and product is maximum. The reaction proceeds via rapid outersphere association complex formation followed by two slow consecutive steps having first order dependence on the aqua ion and thioglycolic acid. Activation parameters have been evaluated using Eyring equation. The low ΔH_1^\ddagger and large negative value of ΔS_1^\ddagger as well as ΔH_2^\ddagger and ΔS_2^\ddagger indicate an associative mode of activation for both aqua molecule substitution process in the two consecutive steps.

Nucleophilic substitution reactions on square-planar complexes of Pt^{II} are of much interest in the field of biomedical research. *cis*-Platin^I, the well known chemotherapeutic reagent having antitumor activity, interacts specifically with DNA. Due to the major toxic effect of *cis*-platin $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2]$, aqua derivatives are now widely used, as one would expect the aqua species to react much faster² in cell than the dichloro species. The reactivity of aquamine complexes of Pt^{II} towards amino acids, nucleosides and nucleotides thus serves as model reactions for the biological systems. In this paper, we have studied the detailed kinetics of aqua molecule substitution by thioglycolic acid in aqueous medium. The interest in the present work is related to the probability of using $[\text{Pt en}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$ as amino acid binder.

Results and Discussion

The $\text{p}K_1$ and $\text{p}K_2$ of thioglycolic acid are 3.58 and 9.78 at 25° respectively³ so that at pH 4 the major species involved in the kinetic process is the anionic form of thioglycolic acid. Since the $\text{p}K_1$ and $\text{p}K_2$ of *cis*-diaquaethylenediamineplatinum(II) ion are 5.8 and 7.6 respectively⁴, we can assume that at pH 4 the reactant exists as the diaqua ion.

The log ($D_\infty - D_t$) versus time plot indicates that the reaction is not a single step process. Here it is assumed to be a two-step consecutive process, both the steps being dependent on the ligand concentrations. The rate constants for the two consecutive steps, $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ and $k_{2(\text{obs})}$ were evaluated as described in literature⁵.

A similar procedure was applied for each ligand concentrations in the range 0.0015–0.006 mol dm⁻³ at constant complex (I) concentrations (0.00015 mol dm⁻³) at pH 4.0 and at different temperatures, viz. 35, 40, 45 and 50°. The $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ values thus obtained increase with the increase in

ligand concentration and at high ligand concentration a limiting rate was observed. The $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ values for ligand concentrations at different temperature are given in Table 1.

Table 1. $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ and $k_{2(\text{obs})}$ values for different ligand concentrations

	Temp. °C	$10^3[\text{Thioglycolic acid}]$ (mol dm ⁻³)			
		1.5	3.0	4.5	6.0
$10^3 k_{1(\text{obs})}$ (s ⁻¹)	35	1.26	2.22	2.98	3.70
	40	1.66	2.85	3.77	4.44
	45	2.19	3.77	4.87	5.71
	50	3.92	6.34	7.40	8.69
$10^5 k_{2(\text{obs})}$ (s ⁻¹)	35	0.75	1.45	2.25	3.75
	40	1.04	2.21	3.11	4.09
	45	1.50	2.99	4.49	5.98
	50	1.96	3.92	5.87	7.83

The ligand concentration dependence of $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ values can be explained in terms of rapid formation of outersphere association complex⁶ between the reactant complex (I) and the S atom of zwitterionic form of the ligand in the A → B stage. The following scheme can be proposed:

Based on the above scheme, a rate expression can be derived for the A → B step,

$$d[B]/dt = k_1 K_E [\text{Pt}(\text{en})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_{\text{total}}^{2+} [\text{S-Thiogly}] / (1 + K_E [\text{S-Thiogly}]) \quad (7)$$

$$\text{or, } d[B]/dt = k_{1(\text{obs})} [\text{Pt}(\text{en})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_{\text{total}}^{2+} \quad (8)$$

where, $[\text{Pt}(\text{en})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_{\text{total}}^{2+}$ is the total concentration of the unreacted complex and we can write,

$$k_{1(\text{obs})} = k_1 K_E [\text{S-Thiogly}] / (1 + K_E [\text{S-Thiogly}]) \quad (9)$$

where, k_1 is the anation rate constant for the A → B step, i.e. the anation rate constant for the interchange of the outersphere complex to the innersphere complex, K_E is the outersphere association equilibrium constant. Equation (9) can be rearranged as

$$1/k_{1(\text{obs})} = 1/k_1 + 1/k_1 K_E [\text{S-Thiogly}] \quad (10)$$

The plot of $1/k_{1(\text{obs})}$ vs $1/[\text{S-Thiogly}]$ should be linear with an intercept of $1/k_1$ and slope of $1/k_1 K_E$. This was found to be so at all temperatures studied. The k_1 and K_E values obtained from the intercept and from the slope to intercept ratios are given in Table 2. The k_2 values (the anation rate constant for the second step) were obtained from the slope of the linear plot of $k_{2(\text{obs})}$ vs [thioglycolic acid].

Table 2. Values of k_1 , k_2 and K_E for the substitution of aqua ligands from $[\text{Pt}(\text{en})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$ by thioglycolic acid

Temp °C	$10^2 k_1$ s^{-1}	$10^3 k_2$ $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$	K_E $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$
35	0.90	5.12	110
40	1.05	7.01	130
45	1.20	10.03	160
50	1.60	12.98	210

The rate constants k_1 and k_2 as well as the outersphere association equilibrium constant (K_E) for the first step are collected in Table 2. The activation parameters for both the steps, calculated from the Eyring plots, are given in Table 3 along with those of analogous systems⁸⁻¹⁰. The temperature variation of K_E is found to fit into the equation, $\ln K_E = -\Delta H^0/RT + \Delta S^0/R$, where $\Delta H^0 = 36.83 \pm 2.55 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $\Delta S^0 = 158.22 \pm 8.07 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$. The positive entropy of formation of the outersphere complex can be attributed to the displacement of water molecule from the outersphere of the hydrated complex ion, $[\text{Pt}(\text{en})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$ by thioglycolic acid.

The formation of outersphere association complex was supported by the rapid intensification of the uv absorbance⁷ of the aqua ion by the addition of ligand at 260 nm. The mechanism of the substitution proceeds through the formation of outersphere association complex followed by two consecutive steps both first order with the metal ion and ligand has been proposed. The sulphur end of the ligand being a soft basic donor atom has a large affinity to the soft acid Pt^{II} centre.

Table 3. Activation parameters

System	$\Delta H_1^\#$ kJ mol^{-1}	$\Delta S_1^\#$ $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$	$\Delta H_2^\#$ kJ mol^{-1}	$\Delta S_2^\#$ $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$
<i>cis</i> -Pt(NH ₃) ₂ (OH) ₂ ²⁺ + 5'-dGMPH ₂ ^a	31.2 ± 4.3	-117 ± 15	60.8 ± 5.3	-55 ± 17.9
<i>cis</i> -Pt(NH ₃) ₂ (OH) ₂ ²⁺ + 5'-GMPH ₂ ^b	40.6 ± 4.4	-106 ± 16	62.8 ± 1.5	-46.3 ± 5.2
<i>cis</i> -Pt en(H ₂ O) ₂ ²⁺ + DL-methionine ^c	15.58 ± 0.9	-230 ± 3.0	19.43 ± 1.2	-225.5 ± 4.0
<i>cis</i> -Pt en(H ₂ O) ₂ ²⁺ + Thioglycolic acid ^d	29.51 ± 4.8	-188 ± 15.3	48.99 ± 1.0	-130 ± 3.1

^aRef. 8. ^bRef. 9. ^cRef. 10. ^dPresent work.

Experimental

The reactant complex $[\text{Pt}(\text{en})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$ (1) was prepared according to the literature method⁴ and characterised spectrally ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 256 \text{ nm}$)¹¹. The product of the reaction between complex (1) and thioglycolic acid was obtained by mixing two reactants at pH 4 in different molar ratios, viz. 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3 and 1 : 4 and thermostated at 60° for 48 h. The absorption spectra of the resultant solutions were recorded and a rapid intensification of the uv absorbance was observed for the stated concentration range indicating some type of metal-ligand association in the initial stage⁶. The composition of the product in the reaction mixture was determined by Job's method of continuous variation. The metal-ligand ratio was found to be 1 : 2.

The pH of the solution was adjusted by adding NaOH/HClO₄ and the measurement was carried out with the help of a Systronics pH meter (accuracy ±0.01). Double-distilled H₂O was used to prepare all the solutions. All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade or purified before use. The reactions were carried out at constant ionic strength (0.1 mol dm⁻³, NaClO₄).

Kinetic measurement was carried out on a Shimadzu UV 2101 PC spectrophotometer equipped with a Shimadzu thermobath (accuracy ±1°). The progress of reaction was monitored by following the increase in absorbance at 224 nm. Conventional mixing technique was followed and pseudo-first order condition was maintained throughout the course of reaction.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the U.G.C., New Delhi, for providing financial assistance under DSA Project in Chemistry. The authors are also thankful to the U.G.C., New Delhi, for providing a Fellowship to one of them (S.G.) and to R. E. College, Durgapur, for providing the necessary assistance and financial help to the other (A.K.G.).

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